

SND Policy for Review of Data and Metadata

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Research data¹ and metadata that are shared in the SND research data catalogue shall have high compliance with the FAIR data principles.² To guarantee this, data and metadata shall be reviewed before they are shared in the SND research data catalogue. The review process shall assess the data, metadata, and documentation with respect to how usable, understandable, and well-documented they are, but *not* to their scientific quality.

This policy applies to research data and metadata that are findable in the SND research data catalogue. It has been approved by the SND Steering Committee and is implemented on all catalogue entries as of 28 September 2021.

1. SND strives to make data and metadata that are described and shared in the SND research data catalogue as compliant with the FAIR principles as possible, in keeping with how the principles are applied in the respective field where the data material is created.
2. Data and metadata that are described and shared in the SND research data catalogue shall be reviewed according to the principles in the document *Krav och rekommendationer för data och metadata i SND:s forskningsdatakatalog (Requirements and Recommendations for Data and Metadata in the SND Research Data Catalogue)*. It is of particular importance that no data are shared in violation of current legislation.
3. Members of the SND network who have local data storage in their respective organisations are responsible for the data and metadata that are shared in the SND research data catalogue. Research principals with local storage can choose to independently review and publish data descriptions in the SND research data catalogue, with support from the SND main office as needed.
4. Data stored by SND CARE shall be reviewed by staff in the SND main office. If the data belong to a research principal who is a member of the SND network, the review can be made by staff at the research principal together with staff at the SND main office.³ In these joint reviews, SND's role is to check that the requirements (see 2 above) are met and to advise during the review process. A detailed description of the routines of joint reviews can be found in the DAU Handbook.⁴
5. Compliance with the SND PID policy.⁵
6. SND shall strive to complete the review of data and metadata within a week of a submitted data description. If more curation is needed or if the researcher needs to supply additional information, the review may take longer. We shall attempt to, as far as possible, accommodate researchers' specific requests for a speedy review process.

¹ Research data are digital material that can form the basis of a scientific analysis, regardless of research field.

² FAIR means that research data shall be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Read more at e.g., [FORCE11](#) or the [Swedish Research Council](#).

³ The research principle determines when they shall be included in the review process.

⁴ <https://dhh.snd.gu.se/wiki/DAU-handboken>

⁵ https://snd.gu.se/sites/default/files/page/SND_pid_policy_antagen_2021-09-28_translation.pdf

7. Considerations, argumentation, and decisions made during the review process shall be documented and stored with the data description. It is of particular importance to document assessments of whether data contain personal data or other protected information.